

RESULTS AND BENEFITS OF ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION IN ACUTE SCROTAL SYNDROME

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Relevance of the problem: Since the 90s of the last century, almost all pediatric surgeons have switched to active surgical tactics for acute testicular diseases in children, the use of ultrasound and Doppler ultrasound both during the acute disease and in the chronic stage, which has led to more accurate diagnosis and successful treatment of the results. [3, 5, 7, 10]. However, in the local literature, issues of hormonal and spermatogenic function in adult men who have suffered acute testicular disease (ATD) in early childhood have been practically not studied. Of particular importance are the optimization of surgical treatment and therapeutic and diagnostic measures in the acute period of the disease, as well as the development of pathogenetic approaches to the postoperative treatment of patients in this contingent [1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 9].

Purpose of the study. Optimization of non-invasive diagnostic methods for acute inflammation of the scrotum in children.

Methods and materials of study: Based on a retrospective analysis, the results of treatment of 202 patients who were treated with a diagnosis of acute testicular disease (ATD) in the emergency surgery and urology departments of the Andijan Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center for 2015-2022 were studied. The clinical material of the study consisted of children aged from 3 months to 18 years. Patients were divided into 3 groups using modern clinical and statistical classification (ICD-10). According to this data, 124 (61.4%) had torsion of the hydatid (epididymis), 57 (28.2%) testicular torsion, epididymitis, orchepididymitis, orchitis 21 (10.0%)

The results of ultrasound and Doppler examination of patients were retrospectively studied. The results of ultrasound examination of 32 scrotums performed for diagnostic purposes in case of ATD are summarized. The echographic picture of acute testicular diseases was characterized by a number of signs and was divided into 2 main groups: specific signs and nonspecific or secondary echosymptoms characteristic of each disease.

The nonspecific echographic criteria for acute testicular disease included the following extratesticular changes: 1. Thickening and layering of the

testicular mucosa on the affected side compared to the contralateral side; 2. Increased blood flow in the testicular mucosa; 3. Accumulation of free fluid in the vaginal cavity.

Nonspecific ultrasound signs were secondary inflammatory changes against the background of scrotal edema-hyperemia syndrome.

In this study, nonspecific ultrasound symptoms were identified in the obvious clinical picture of the disease: complication of hydatid torsion, testicular torsion, epididymitis and epididymorchitis.

In uncomplicated hydatid torsion and subclinical orchitis, no secondary inflammatory changes were detected. Nonspecific echosymptoms in traumatic injuries were found only in the case of hematoma of the testicular mucosa and testicular rupture.

Results of the study. Ultrasound diagnostic criteria for testicular torsion during ultrasound are: a sharp decrease in blood flow in the internal organs (up to its disappearance) or its increase by 2-4 times along with an increase in the size and composition of the testicle, ultrasound diagnostic criteria for hydatid torsion in ultrasound: significant (>20%) enlargement or enlargement of the epididymis with an increase in blood flow up to 10% of normal and heterogeneity of composition are ultrasound diagnostic criteria for acute epididymitis with Doppler ultrasound: moderate enlargement or homogeneity of the epididymis. with a moderate increase in blood flow (up to 10%), an increase in blood flow up to 10% of normal in combination with an increase in the size of the testicle and the heterogeneity of its composition are ultrasound diagnostic criteria for acute orchitis in ultrasound diagnostics. The sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound symptoms in acute testicular diseases in young children do not depend on the stage of the disease, and the sensitivity and specificity of clinical signs increase significantly with late presentation to the hospital.

Conclusion. In patients with testicular torsion, the echographic picture is characterized by clear changes. The pathognomonic echographic sign of testicular torsion is a slowdown or loss of blood flow in its parenchyma with increased blood flow in the testicular membrane.

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